

16th International Conference on Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies, GHGT-16

23rd -27th October 2022, Lyon, France

Compression and liquefaction unit for measuring impurities in the CO₂

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Abstract

A new CO₂ Compression and Liquefaction Unit (CCLU) for measuring impurities in the CO₂ product has been built, commissioned, and connected to the CO₂ capture pilot plant at SINTEF. The unit will be used to measure impurities in the CO₂ after compression and drying at conditions relevant to CO₂ shipping or transport. The CCLU has been designed with components like an industrial-sized unit, with three compressor stages including cooling and condensate knock-out drums. After being compressed to 35 - 40 bar, the CO₂ gas is dried and then cooled down and liquefied at -5 to -10 °C by an external cooler. The liquefied CO₂ is then expanded to 16 bars through an expansion valve and stored at -24.4 °C in a storage tank.

Liquid samples are taken from the knock-out drums whilst gas samples are extracted upstream of the external cooler. It is also possible to take a sample of the gas out of the storage tank. In a short test campaign with 30 wt% MEA, the CCLU has shown to operate well and have a fast response to steady-state conditions.

Keywords: CO₂ Compression and Liquefaction; Chemical Absorption; Carbon Capture; MEA;

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Quality of the CO₂ coming out from the capture unit can be crucial for transportation, storage and usage of CO₂. For example, besides strict limitations of compounds like O₂, N₂, NO_x, SO₂ coming from the flue gas, the Northern Light project also has limit levels of amines and amine degradation products. For amines and ammonia, the level for transportation is ≤10 ppm while for degradation products like aldehydes, it is ≤20 ppm. The knowledge about amount and impact of these compounds are generally not well known. Typically, the compounds found in the exhaust gas leaving the absorber are also present to some extent in the CO₂ stream out of the desorber. The following compression stages produce knock-out water in condensate drums and probably much of the impurities follow the water. In the last stage, we get liquefied CO₂. Besides that, a small amount of water is soluble in the CO₂, the solubility of amines and amine degradation products in liquid CO₂ is usually unknown.

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1.2. SINTEF's Tiller CO₂Lab

The CO₂ laboratory at Tiller (Tiller CO₂Lab) is a highly equipped test facility for the development of post-combustion CO₂ capture technologies, as well as a research lab for flue gas pre-treatment analysis and emission research.

The pilot plant (Figure 1) was built and commissioned in 2010 inside a 30 m high building. Flue gas is provided by a propane burner that heats up the surrounding buildings and contains about 11% CO₂ (dry). However, by recirculating some of the captured CO₂ and/or diluting it with ambient air various concentrations of CO₂ in the feed gas can be specified. The absorber packing height is 19.5 m while the packing height in the stripper column is 13.6 m. These heights are comparable with full-scale industrial columns. At the top of the absorber and desorber columns, there are two sections with water wash to reduce the emissions of amines in the gas leaving the columns. The amount of CO₂ out of the desorber is typically 20-40 kg/h depending on the amount of flue gas treated.

The entire system is controlled by a Siemens PCS7 process control system and the plant can operate 24 hours a day. The plant is constructed for accurate measurements of key process variables including:

- Energy requirements
- Absorption capacity
- Emissions to air
- Degradation of solvents
- Other key process parameters

The results of these measurements combined with analyses of gas and liquid samples are important input parameters to SINTEF's simulation tool CO₂SIM. This simulation tool can be used for modelling and optimization of large-scale plants, based on pilot validation.

More information of the plant is found in [1].

Figure 1 The full height absorber and desorber inside the 30m high building.

1.3. The REALISE project

The present work is a part of the EU Horizon 2020 project "Demonstration of a refinery-adapted cluster-integrated strategy to enable full-chain CCUS implementation" (REALISE). In this project, the pilot plant at Tiller will be used in a 12-weeklong campaign from August to November 2022. The campaign will

- Find optimal L/G giving the minimum specific thermal reboiler duty in terms of MJ/kg CO₂, for both 90 and 95% capture rate.
- Provide reliable steady-state data for verification of simulation models and dynamic step response data for validating dynamic models.
- Demonstrate Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC) of the plant for large disturbances and changes in flue gas rates and CO₂ concentrations
- Measure degradation of the solvent. Degraded solvent from the Irving will be mixed in with fresh solvent to mimic a partly reclaimed solvent.
- Measure emissions of solvent and solvent degradation products in the gas out of the absorber
- Measure impurities in the compressed and liquified CO₂ product for assessment and de-risking of CO₂ utilization and CO₂ transport.

Before the campaign started a compact CO₂ compression and liquefaction unit (CCLU) was designed, constructed and commissioned at Tiller. This activity is described in the present paper.

2. Design of the Compression and Liquefaction Unit (CCLU)

Quality of the CO₂ coming out from the capture unit can be crucial for transportation, storage and utilization of CO₂. In REALISE the main objective is to identify and quantify expected impurities in the CO₂ product when using HS-3 solvent (40 wt% 1-(2-Hydroxyethyl)pyrrolidine and 15 wt% of 3-amino-1-propanol) in the refinery industry. The focus is on HS-3 amines and amine degradation products in the CO₂, but also compounds like O₂ and NO_x will be measured.

In the design of the CCLU it has been an important issue to be as close to a large-scale standard unit as possible such that the results at Tiller are relevant for industrial cases.

The development of the P&ID was largely based upon the findings and recommendations from successive HAZOP study series as well as subsequent technical discussions in some of the project meetings. The resultant suggestions, changes and improvements were incorporated into the P&ID yielding a refined version each time, until it was considered to contain adequate detail deemed satisfactory by the technical team. This is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Schematic showing the evolution of the P&ID based on HAZOP analysis studies.

For safety reasons the CCLU is built inside a cabinet with ventilation and CO₂ level alarm.

2.1. Compression train

The compressor train design is based on three compression stages with cooling of the gas to 20 - 25 °C and water separation after each stage. The design compressor ratio for each stage is 2.8. Assuming 1.8 bara pressure for the CO₂ rich gas from the top of the desorber this will give pressures of about 5, 14, and 40 bara after each stage. The PI&D of the compression train is shown in Figure 2 1.

Figure 3 The P&ID Compression part of the CCLU. The CO₂ from the stripper enters the figure at the bottom and leaves at the top.

The compressor stages are implemented using Haskell gas boosters from Proserv. This use compressed air to drive the piston in the boosters. At SINTEF Tiller such air is available for the whole area from a central compressor. Even if the design compression ratio is 2.8 they have some flexibility for increasing/decreasing this ratio.

The amount of CO₂ taken from the stripper CO₂ product stream is measured by a Coriolis flow meter (FT300). Also, the inlet temperature is measured (TI300). The gas then enters the first compression stage at approximately 1.5-1.8 bar and leaves it at approximately 5 bars by using the first Haskell gas booster. The gas is then cooled down to 15-20 °C and the condensed component (water or other condensates) is separated out in a knockout drum. The gas is then sent to a second Haskell booster which increases the pressure to about 14 bar and then to the third booster which gives about 35-40 bar. There are knock-out drums after each of these two compressors as well. It is possible to take liquid samples from the drums.

Figure 4 The three compressors a) Front view b) back view with pipes, valves and knock-out drums

Figure 4 shows the front panel for the three boosters. These are accessible through cut-outs in the cabinet. Figure 4b shows the piping and knock-out drums inside the cabinet.

2.2. Dryers

After the third knock-out drum the compressed CO₂ gas is at 35 - 40 bar and 15 - 25 °C. The pressure is controlled by a control valve. The gas will then have 400 – 600 ppm of water. To get down to 20 – 30 ppm that is often required, the gas is dried in a cylinder filled with molecular sieve 3Å beads. Two such cylinders are mounted in parallel (see Figure 2 2) to increase the flexibility of the system.

Figure 5 The drying system of the CCLU

2.3. Liquefaction

An external Lauda Integral IN 250XTW cooler (See Figure 6) provides a cooling medium (ethanol) at typically -5 to -15 °C. The CO_2 gas is liquified with this ethanol inside a plate and frame heat exchanger. The temperature of the liquid CO_2 is typically -5 to -10 °C.

Figure 6. a) The external cooler Lauda.

b) Cooling and expansion of CO_2

Afterwards, the liquid is expanded through an expansion valve CrV303 to the desired pressure (15-16 bar). This will produce a two-phase stream at about -26 °C that enters a CO_2 storage tank (Carbo-Max 450) produced by Linde (Figure 6).

The gas phase will leave the tank through a control valve that keeps the pressure at 15 -16 bar. The liquid will be stored in the tank. The tank is well insulated, and any heat loss will be compensated by evaporation of liquid CO_2 and released through the control valve.

The gas out of the tank may either leave the unit to ventilation or be led back to the last stage compressor.

Figure 7. The CO₂ storage tank Carbo-Max 450.

3. Commissioning and testing

The commissioning and testing of the CCLU was done in three periods starting with 18th and 19th of January where only the compression train was tested. The next period was in 10th, 14th and 15th of March where the complete unit was tested. After doing some modifications of the unit the final test run was done the 4th of April. Data from this test will be shown in the following.

3.1. Compression train

In Figure 8 data from the pressure sensors are shown. The test started at 12:30 where the three Haskel boosters was started in sequence from low to high pressure. As can be seen from the figure the compression system came quickly to a steady state condition and kept the pressure until they were shut down around 14:36.

The temperatures in the compression train are shown in Figure 8. The cooling after each stage is efficient and the temperature becomes constant after only 10 – 15 minutes. The temperature after the second and third compressor is constant after approximately 30 minutes while the temperature after the first compressor takes somewhat more time to be constant. However, for the conditions downstream the compression train these temperatures are not important.

Figure 8. The pressure at each stage.

Figure 9. The temperature before and after cooling at each stage.

3.2. Drying

In Figure 10 the temperature after drying section is shown together with the temperature before and after the 3rd stage separator. The temperature increases downstream the 3rd cooler by about 5-6 °C due to heat transfer from the room temperature in the cabinet.

Figure 10. The temperature downstream the 3rd stage cooling.

3.3. Liquefaction

In Figure 11 the temperatures after the dryer, heat exchanger with ethanol from Lauda cooler and expansion valve are shown. In the beginning the temperature after liquefaction is 4.7 °C. At 13:20 the setpoint for the ethanol temperature was changed and the liquid CO₂ became -15.8 °C. However, the temperature after expansion (-24.4 °C) was not affected because it is determined by the pressure level in the Carbo-Max tank which was constant during the test.

Figure 11. The temperature before and after liquefaction and after expansion.

This is shown in Figure 12. The pressure in Carbo-Max is constant all the time, also before the test started because CO₂ had been stored in the tank from earlier tests. The figure also shows the pressure drop from 3rd compressor to the expansion which was 1.2 bar.

Figure 12. The pressure before and after the expansion valve.

Figure 13. Gas flow rates into and out of the CCLU.

Figure 13 shows the measured gas flow into the CCLU and the measured gas flow out of the Carbo-Max. The last one is rather noisy because this flow is used to control the pressure in the tank. However, the filtered signal shows that it was around 3.2 kg/h in the first part of the test and 2.4 kg/h the last part. The decreased temperature of the liquid before expansion gave a lower gas/liquid fraction after expansion. After being constant the flow into the CCLU was 10.6 kg/h. This means that 7.4 kg/h in the first part and 8.2 kg/h in the second part was stored in the tank as liquid CO₂.

3.4. The Carbo-Max storage tank

Between the testing periods, the CO₂ in the Carbo-Max 450 tank was stored. Even if the tank is well insulated the temperature difference between the tank (-24.4 °C) and the room (~20 °C) is more than 40 °C and heat will be transferred to the tank. This heat will evaporate some of the liquid CO₂ and the pressure will increase. The pressure control valve will then release some gas to keep the pressure at 16 bar.

Figure 14 is taken from the Siemens PCS7 control system and illustrates a period where the CCLU was not running and producing CO₂ Figure 14.

Figure 14. Gas flow rate from the storage tank at regular time intervals.

The flow is zero except from some spikes at regular intervals of about 40 minutes. In Figure 15 a spike is enlarged and shows that it lasts for about 30 seconds.

By using the spike frequency and integrating one spike the loss of CO₂ under storage is estimated to be 38 g/h or less than one kg pr day.

Figure 15. Gas flow rate from the storage tank during a few seconds.

4. Conclusions

A CO₂ Compression and Liquefaction Unit (CCLU) has been designed and built at the Tiller CO₂Lab. The CCLU was designed with components like an industrial sized unit with three compressor stages including cooling and knock out drums. Out of the last drum the CO₂ gas at 35 - 40 bar is dried and then cooled down to about -5 to -10 °C by an external cooler. The liquefied CO₂ is then expanded to 16 bar through an expansion valve and stored at -24.4 °C in a storage tank.

Samples of liquid is taken from the knockout drums and samples of the gas before the external cooler. It is also possible to take a sample of the gas out of the storage tank.

Risk assessment measures that include HAZID, both classical and procedural HAZOP studies have been performed. These yielded a robust and optimal design that is characterized by safe operability and enhanced efficiency.

The Lauda Integral cooler could cool the liquid CO₂ to less than -15 °C

The Carbo-Max storage tank was tested both at 15 and 16 bar. The temperature was -26.3 and -24.4 °C respectively. The storage tank could store the CO₂ with a loss less than 1 kg of CO₂ per day.

Acknowledgements

This work was a part of the REALISE project which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 884266.

References

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